

REGIONAL COOPERATION IN CULTURAL DIPLOMACY IN CENTRAL ASIA: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract: Cultural diplomacy in Central Asia has become an important tool for strengthening national identity, regional integration and international image. The study shows the stages of its development: from the approval of symbols in the 1990s to institutionalization within the CIS, SCO and TURKSOY, as well as the digital transformation of recent years. The main problems are highlighted - competition for heritage, language differences and external influence, as well as opportunities through common cultural symbols and international organizations.

Key words: Central Asia, cultural diplomacy, national identity, regional cooperation, soft power, international organizations, integration.

Introduction

In the Central Asian states, after gaining independence, cultural diplomacy has become one of the key instruments for forming national identity and strengthening the international image ¹. From the first years of independence, cultural projects have become an integral part of the policy of legitimizing power: in Uzbekistan, special attention was paid to the figure of Amir Temur, in Kazakhstan - to the idea of the "Great Steppe" and the creative heritage of Abai Kunanbayev ². These symbols served not only as a means of consolidating society, but also as a foreign policy resource, allowing the new states to be positioned as bearers of a unique historical and cultural heritage. At the same time, multilateral cooperation platforms were being formed: within the framework of the CIS, SCO, TURKSOY, and OIC, cultural programs aimed at supporting common civilizational memory and strengthening regional solidarity were actively developed.

The relevance of the study is determined by the fact that cultural diplomacy in the context of Central Asia performs a dual function. On the one hand, it promotes internal consolidation and strengthening of national statehood. On the other hand, it becomes a means of "soft power" aimed at forming an attractive

¹Marat, E. Nation Branding in Central Asia: A New Campaign to Present Ideas about the State and the Nation. *Europe-Asia Studies*, 61(7), 1123–1136. 2009.

²Chang, X., & Bo, Y. The strategy of the state cultural policy in Kazakhstan: evolution, implementation, and efficiency. *Voprosy Istorii*, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.31166/voprosyistorii202312statyi51>

image of the region in the external environment, attracting investments and developing tourism. Thus, cultural diplomacy acts as a link between identity politics, economic modernization and international integration.

However, the practice of cultural interaction faces a number of serious obstacles. First of all, this is competition around historical figures and cultural heritage. For example, the legacy of Alisher Navoi is interpreted differently in Uzbekistan and Tajikistan, which gives rise to disputes about the “ownership” of cultural symbols ³. A similar situation is developing around the images of Jaloliddin Manguberdi or Babur. The second important factor is language policy: de-Russification, the transition to the Latin alphabet, and the desire for linguistic purism create barriers to interstate communication ⁴. The third source of tension is border and water disputes (for example, in the Fergana Valley), which negatively affect the atmosphere of trust between the countries ⁵. Finally, external actors have a significant influence - Russia, China, Turkey and Iran, each of which promotes its own cultural strategies, forming parallel and often competing narratives in the region ⁶.

The aim of the dissertation research is to analyze the processes of formation and development of cultural diplomacy in Central Asia, identify its institutional mechanisms, practical forms, main obstacles and opportunities for deepening regional integration. The object of the study is the processes of regional cultural interaction; the subject is institutional mechanisms, the role of state and non-state actors, as well as discursive practices in the field of cultural diplomacy.

The methodological basis of the study is based on classical and modern theories of international relations: realism (interests and power), liberalism (interdependence and norms), constructivism (identity and social practices), the concept of "soft power" by J. Nye ⁷, the theory of cultural hegemony by A. Gramsci, the globalization approaches of A. Appadurai, as well as the methods of Actor-Network Theory (ANT), which allow us to consider cultural diplomacy as a result of the interaction of various actors - government agencies, international

³Fierman, W. Identity, Symbolism, and the Politics of Language in Central Asia. *Europe-Asia Studies*, 61(7), 1207–1228. 2009.

⁴Edgina, G., Djumabekov, D., Zueva, L., Dosova, B., & Kozina, V. Language Policy in Kazakhstan in the Context of World Practice. *Journal of Nationalism, Memory & Language Politics*, 17. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jnmlp-2023-0004>

⁵Karasik, S. Water, Conflict, and Cooperation in Central Asia: The Role of International Law and Diplomacy. *Vermont Journal of Environmental Law*, 18, 400–432. 2017.

⁶Niemiec, J.M. Preserving Common Ties: Turkey's Public Diplomacy in Central Asia. *Annales UMCS*, Vol. 9, 241–262. 2024.

⁷Papaioannou, K. Cultural diplomacy in international relations. *IJASOS*, 3, 942–944. 2017. <https://doi.org/10.18769/IJASOS.367306>

cultural centers (British Council, Goethe Institute, Yunus Emre Institute), NGOs, universities, diasporas, artists and digital platforms ⁸.

The working hypothesis of the study is that cultural diplomacy can become a factor in regional integration, provided that there is a transnational interpretation of common heritage and the active involvement of new actors - the diaspora, youth and digital communities. The development of digital diplomacy is of particular importance, especially after the COVID-19 pandemic, when online exhibitions, virtual festivals and digital archives have become the main channel for promoting cultural heritage.

The practical significance of the work is that its conclusions and recommendations can be used by ministries of culture, foreign policy agencies and specialized institutes to develop joint programs, coordinate language policies, prepare cross-border nominations for UNESCO lists, institutionalize digital diplomacy and develop strategies for interaction with the diaspora ⁹. The structure of the dissertation includes an introduction, three chapters (theoretical foundations, practice and problems, opportunities and strategic approaches), a conclusion with recommendations and a list of references.

Main part

Cultural diplomacy in Central Asia has gone through several stages of development since the collapse of the USSR, reflecting the internal and foreign policy transformations of the region's states. In the 1990s, the key task was to form a national identity and symbolic legitimization of new states. In Uzbekistan, the central place was occupied by the image of Amir Temur: his cult was actively used in the official ideology, and 1996 was declared the "year of Amir Temur", which was accompanied by large-scale commemorative events and the creation of the State Museum of the Timurids in Tashkent. During the same period, Kazakhstan focused on the figure of Abai Kunanbayev and the concept of the "Great Steppe", which allowed it to establish cultural markers of national identity in a multi-ethnic society ¹⁰. Language policy also played an important role: in Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan, the transition to the Latin alphabet began, while in Kazakhstan, the policy of "Kazakhization" was aimed at strengthening the role of the state language. These processes indicate that culture was viewed as a strategic resource for nationalization and distancing from the Soviet past.

⁸Yunus Emre Institute. The Role of Yunus Emre Institutes in the Educational and Cultural Diplomacy of Turkey. Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology, 23(3), 140–150. 2024.

⁹UNESCO. Silk Roads World Heritage Serial and Transnational Nomination in Central Asia. <https://whc.unesco.org/en/activities/870>

¹⁰Olcott, MB Kazakhstan: Unfulfilled Promise. Washington DC: Carnegie Endowment, 2002. p. 37.

In the early 2000s, cultural diplomacy acquired institutional forms and went beyond national borders. Kazakhstan launched the state program “Madeni Mura” (2004), which included archaeological research, the publication of hundreds of volumes of national literature, and the restoration of cultural monuments ¹¹. This program became an example of a systemic cultural policy aimed at both internal self-affirmation and international recognition, including active interaction with UNESCO. During this period, Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan began to actively hold bilateral cultural events, including “days of culture,” joint exhibitions, and festivals. At the same time, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization and the CIS consolidated the cultural dimension in their institutions, making cultural exchange part of the official cooperation agenda.

A landmark event was the inclusion of Navruz in the UNESCO List of Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity in 2009. This step emphasized the role of common traditions as symbols of regional unity. In the 2010s, Central Asian cultural diplomacy was increasingly used for global positioning. Uzbekistan organized international exhibitions dedicated to Samarkand and Bukhara in Paris and Berlin, collaborating with UNESCO and the Louvre ¹². Kazakhstan developed a cultural dimension through participation in international expos, and Turkmenistan used the symbol of the Akhal-Teke horse as a key element of its image on the world stage.

Since 2016, cultural diplomacy has gained new momentum. Uzbekistan has increased its focus on cultural cooperation within the framework of openness in foreign policy, and contacts with international cultural centers have been intensified. At the same time, Kazakhstan focused on “Rukhani Zhangyru” (“Spiritual Renewal”), the program of which included projects to preserve historical memory and promote cultural values in a global context. Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan focused on the Manas epic and the figure of Ismaili Somoni as the foundations of national narratives, while trying to promote them through international cultural formats.

Disputes over the legacy of historical figures, which are interpreted differently in different countries, remain an important challenge for cultural diplomacy. For example, the figure of Navoi can be perceived as a common cultural symbol, but at the same time cause competition between Uzbekistan and Tajikistan. Differences in language policies also create additional barriers: some countries have switched to the Latin alphabet, while others have retained

¹¹Melich, J., & Adibayeva, A. Nation-Building and Cultural Policy in Kazakhstan. 2014.

¹²Fierman, W. A Comparative Examination of Language Ecology and Language Policy in Post-Soviet Central Asia. Al-Farabi, 2021.

the Cyrillic alphabet¹³. Unresolved border and water disputes increase mutual mistrust and limit the space for cooperation. An additional factor is the cultural policy of external actors: Russia promotes the Russian language and Orthodox heritage through Rossotrudnichestvo, Turkey expands its influence through the Yunus Emre Institute, China uses cultural projects within the framework of the Belt and Road initiative, and Iran appeals to Islamic and Persian cultural heritage. All this forms a field of competing narratives and requires a delicate diplomatic balance from the Central Asian states.

Despite these challenges, the region's cultural diplomacy shows sustainable potential. Shared symbols such as Nowruz and the Silk Road can serve as tools for building a common identity, while international organizations such as UNESCO, the SCO, TURKSOY, and the Organization of Turkic States provide institutional mechanisms for implementing joint initiatives. The COVID-19 pandemic has shown new opportunities for digital diplomacy: events have been moved online, virtual exhibitions and festivals have been created, opening up prospects for further expansion of audiences and youth engagement. Thus, cultural diplomacy in Central Asia is not only an image policy tool, but also an important channel for regional integration based on a combination of national interests and common cultural values.

Conclusion and recommendations

Cultural diplomacy in Central Asia in the post-Soviet period has become one of the key instruments of both internal development and international positioning of all five republics of the region – Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan. Over three decades, it has gone through several stages: from the assertion of national identity in the 1990s to the institutionalization of cultural cooperation in the 2000s, from global branding in the 2010s to digital transformation and expansion of the actor composition in recent years.

The key result is that culture has been transformed into a universal resource. In the 1990s, each state chose its own symbols to legitimize its sovereignty: in Uzbekistan, the figure of Amir Temur, in Kazakhstan, Abai and the “Great Steppe,” in Tajikistan, Ismaili Somoni, in Kyrgyzstan, the Manas epic, and in Turkmenistan, the image of the Akhal-Teke horse and ancient oases. In the 2000s, cultural diplomacy reached the regional and international levels through programs such as “Madeni Mura” in Kazakhstan, bilateral “days of culture,” and the participation of all countries in the region in the CIS, SCO,

¹³Izteleuova, E. Foreign Policy of Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan: Main Directions and Achievements. Journal of International Relations and Regional Studies, 2023.

TURKSOY, and OIC formats. An important unifying symbol was Navruz, which in 2009 was recognized by UNESCO as an intangible heritage of humanity and became a platform for the collective representation of Central Asia on the world stage. In the 2010s, the Silk Road gained particular importance as a regional identity brand: states began to promote historical cities, epics, and traditions as part of tourism and exhibition projects. After 2016, cultural diplomacy acquired a new dimension - digital and multi-actor: diasporas, universities, international cultural centers (the British Council, the Goethe Institute, the Yunus Emre Institute) actively joined in, and the COVID-19 pandemic consolidated online formats of cultural exchange ¹⁴.

The main challenges of regional cultural diplomacy are related to competition over historical heritage (for example, over the figures of Navoi, Babur or Manas), differences in language policy (Latin/Cyrillic), unresolved border and water issues, and the strong presence of external actors – Russia, China, Turkey and Iran – promoting their cultural models and interests. These factors limit the possibilities for a unified cultural policy, increase fragmentation and create a field of competing narratives.

At the same time, significant potential remains. Central Asia has a unique historical and cultural heritage that can be used as a unifying resource. Symbols such as Navruz, the Manas epic, the image of Samarkand and Bukhara, the heritage of the Somonids or the ancient cities of Turkmenistan can form a common regional identity. International institutions (UNESCO, SCO, TURKSOY, the Organization of Turkic States) provide platforms for coordination. New digital technologies make it possible to broadcast culture beyond the region, engaging a wide audience.

Based on this, three priority areas can be identified as recommendations.

First, the creation of a regional council for cultural diplomacy in Central Asia, which will unite the efforts of all five republics in developing joint strategies.

Secondly, the formation of a unified digital platform for Central Asia, where cultural heritage, educational projects and festivals will be presented and accessible to a global audience.

Thirdly, special attention should be paid to youth: developing interstate exchange programs, supporting youth initiatives and involving new generations in promoting the cultural identity of the region.

¹⁴Yalinkiliçli, E. Uzbekistan as a Gateway for Turkey's Return to Central Asia. *Insight Turkey*, 20, 27–43. 2018.

These steps will help transform cultural diplomacy from a set of individual national projects into a real instrument of regional integration and strengthening the global image of Central Asia.

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